

FINAL REPORT

SPOKE 1: MOUNTAIN INNOVATION ECOSYSTEM

PROJECT NAME: Sediment Management in Hydropower Reservoirs: a comprehensive approach (SMAHR)

The Final Report relates to the scientific activities carried out and the results achieved within the project funded through the Young Researcher Call for Proposals: it must provide a comprehensive description of the project results, with specific reference to the project activities carried out, the progress made and the achievement of the milestones and targets set out in the approved project.

The Final Report is submitted by the PI (principal investigator) and is evaluated by the Scientific Committee, in accordance with the provisions of the aforementioned Call for Proposals.

The Final Report must underscore these aspects:

- the final objectives achieved and set out in the project submitted for evaluation, as well as any deviations from the established objectives and the reasons for such deviations;
- any deviations between the approved Economic and Financial Plan and the reported costs, that must be justified.

PROJECT DETAILS	
Spoke	1 – Mountain Innovation Ecosystem
PROJECT ACRONYM	SMAHR
PI – Principal Investigator - University	Pisaturo Giuseppe Roberto
Starting date:	04/10/2024
Duration:	12 months
Ending date:	03/10/2025
<i>Other participants - university</i>	Righetti Maurizio

Annexes:

<i>Possible annex</i>	
<i>Possible annex</i>	

Date: -----

PI signature: -----

1. Technical and scientific results of the project

1.1. Description of the final results achieved

Maximum two pages.

Images and diagrams may be attached at the end of the report. Indicate whether the expected results were achieved, explaining and quantifying any deviations.

Describe the expected and actual results of the project in qualitative terms.

The main objective of the SMAHR project was to provide practical guidance to hydropower plant operators for the proper management of sediments deposited within artificial reservoirs. In order to achieve this overarching goal, the project was structured around several sub-objectives, covering both experimental activities and numerical modelling approaches.

The original objectives included the development of an experimental laboratory setup aimed at reconstructing near-bed velocity profiles in riverine environments, with the purpose of improving the understanding of the effects of bed shear stress on sediment transport processes. In addition, the project aimed at performing numerical simulations on at least one case study, focusing on both hydrodynamic and habitat modelling in response to sediment flushing operations.

Most of the planned activities were successfully carried out during the project period. In particular, the following key results were achieved:

1. The commissioning of an experimental setup for the study of velocity profiles near the bed, as well as the development of an additional setup for investigating turbidity current dynamics.
2. The implementation of a velocity profile formulation for flows over rough beds.
3. Initial attempts to predict suspended sediment transport input to hydropower reservoirs using machine learning techniques.
4. Numerical modelling of an artificial reservoir (Fortezza) to support sediment management strategies.
5. Numerical modelling of a reach of the Rienza River to assess the ecological effects of sediment flushing operations on river habitat.

The current standard management practice for reservoirs typically involves periodic sediment removal every 4–6 years through controlled opening of bottom outlets. This approach induces significant stress on downstream ecosystems due to prolonged periods (10–15 days) of high discharges and, in particular, very high suspended sediment concentrations (SSC).

The results obtained from the research activities carried out within the SMAHR project highlighted alternative reservoir management strategies aimed at reducing the ecological impacts associated with sediment removal. Specifically, both the modelling of reservoir behaviour and the assessment of ecological effects of flushing operations indicate that, at least for the analysed case study, the current management approach should be replaced by a strategy based on more frequent flushing events (potentially on an annual basis), characterized by significantly lower water volumes and reduced suspended sediment loads.

Such an approach would substantially mitigate the impact on downstream ecosystems, allow flushing operations to be carried out during periods of naturally high flows driven by precipitation, and render the dam nearly transparent to sediment concentration waves during flood events. The main outcome of the project therefore consists in proposing a feasible modification of reservoir management practices to hydropower operators, where applicable. In support of these findings, the contacted operator has already started exploring pilot implementations of the proposed management strategy.

Highlight the starting and final TRL (Technology Readiness Level) and the main KPI (Key Performance Indicator) achieved

The project focused on the study of techniques for improving sediment management in hydropower reservoirs. Consequently, it did not result in the development of new material technologies or prototypes, but rather in the generation of new scientific knowledge and the formulation of management concepts aimed at minimizing the ecological impact of flushing operations while ensuring downstream hydraulic safety.

At the beginning of the project, the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) was TRL 1, corresponding to the observation of basic principles and initial scientific research. By the end of the project, the TRL reached TRL 2, as the technological and operational concepts for improved sediment management were formulated and clearly defined, based on analytical studies and application to real case scenarios.

The main Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) achieved include:

- formulation of conceptual strategies for environmentally sustainable sediment flushing;
- improved understanding of sediment transport and deposition processes in hydropower reservoirs;
- qualitative and quantitative assessment of potential ecological impacts of flushing operations;
- support to decision-making through the definition of preliminary operational guidelines for reservoir sediment management.

Describe the External Partners who collaborated, their contribution, and the possible synergies that may continue in the near future

The main External Partners involved in the SMAHR project were both private and public stakeholders, each contributing specific expertise and data essential to the achievement of the project objectives.

1. **Cartorender.** Cartorender carried out the bathymetric survey operations as foreseen in the project plan. The high-resolution bathymetric data provided by Cartorender were fundamental for the characterization of sediment deposition within the reservoirs and for the setup and calibration of the numerical models.
2. **Alperia.** Alperia contributed by sharing detailed data related to hydropower plant management, including information on reservoir operation and the volumes of sediments removed during previous flushing operations. This input was crucial to ensure that the modelling activities and the proposed management strategies were grounded in real operational conditions and constraints.
3. **Civil Protection Agency.** Interactions with the Civil Protection Agency focused on understanding whether alternative reservoir management strategies could be compatible with the use of reservoirs for flood mitigation purposes. These discussions helped to frame sediment management not only from an environmental and operational perspective, but also within a broader territorial risk management context.

With all three partners, both private and public, a strong and ongoing collaboration is envisaged in the field of hydropower reservoir management. In particular, with Cartorender and Alperia, data and results sharing agreements are already in place, allowing continuous exchange of information and mutual updates on ongoing and future activities. This is especially relevant given the strategic importance of sediment management for hydropower plant operation.

Furthermore, collaboration with the Civil Protection Agency is expected to continue in the near future through joint research activities related to flood management in the South Tyrol region. These synergies are expected to support the development of integrated reservoir management strategies that simultaneously address sediment continuity, ecological impacts, and flood risk reduction.

1.2. Summary of deliverables

Name	Result ¹	Links	TRL ²	Description and references
	[SCI] [PROD] [SERV] [PROC] [BUS] [DSG] [METH] [PO]	Link to Zenodo or BIA	[TRL4] [TRL5] [TRL6] [TRL7] [TRL8] [N.A.]	[Publication] [Prototyping in laboratory environment] [Prototyping in production environment] [Pilot, demonstrator or test] [Intellectual property management] [Patent submission] [Other]
Velocity Profiles in Gravel Beds Based on Refractive Index Matching Experiments	SCI	10.1061/JHEND8.HYENG-14131	N.A.	Publication
Sediment transport from basin to reservoir: the case of the Fortezza dam in the Italian Alps	SCI	Under publication on "Sediment management in rivers and reservoirs: examples from Europe and China", GeoPlanet: Earth and Planetary Sciences series by Springer	N.A.	Publication
Predict suspended sediment concentration in an alpine stream using data-driven modelling	SCI	Presentation at the IAHR 2025 conference in Singapore	N.A.	Conference presentation

¹ [SCI — Scientific discovery, model, theory, etc.] [PROD — Product (new or improved)] [SERV — Service (new or improved)] [PROC — Industrial process (new or improved)] [BUS — Business model (new or improved)] [DSG — Design (new or improved)] [METH — Method, material, technology, design (new or improved)]

² [TRL4 - Technology validated in the laboratory] [TRL5 - Technology validated in the relevant environment] [TRL6 - Technology demonstrated in a relevant environment] [TRL7 - Demonstration of the prototype system in an operational environment] [TRL8 - Complete and qualified system] [TRL9 - Real system tested in an operational environment] [Not applicable]

2. COMPLIANCE WITH CONDITIONALITIES AND ALL ADDITIONAL REQUIREMENTS RELATED TO THE PNRR MEASURES

2.1. DNSH principle and legislation provided for by the Environmental Code

Description of how the activities carried out comply with the DNSH principle and legislation provided for by the Environmental Code. In this regard, the reasons why the activities carried out do not cause significant harm to each of the environmental objectives are reported.

Environment	Has the DNSH principle been respected for the environmental objective? (Y/N) ³	Justifications:
1. Climate change mitigation	Y	The project activities do not generate greenhouse gas emissions nor increase climate-related risks. On the contrary, the proposed sediment management strategies are expected to enhance the long-term efficiency and resilience of hydropower systems, supporting renewable energy production and adaptation to changing hydrological regimes.
2. Climate change adaptation	Y	The project activities do not generate greenhouse gas emissions nor increase climate-related risks. On the contrary, the proposed sediment management strategies are expected to enhance the long-term efficiency and resilience of hydropower systems, supporting renewable energy production and adaptation to changing hydrological regimes.
3. Sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources	Y	All activities were designed to improve the understanding and management of sediment dynamics in reservoirs and downstream river reaches. The numerical modelling and experimental analyses aim to reduce the ecological impacts associated with current sediment flushing practices, contributing to a more balanced interaction between reservoir operation and river systems. No activities involved the direct alteration of water bodies or unauthorized discharges.

³ If the activities carried out do not have an impact on the environmental objective, it is appropriate to answer "Yes", in case of "Not", enter the reasons in the "Justifications" column of the same table..

4. Transition to a circular economy, including waste reduction and recycling	Y	The project activities are based on data analysis, modelling, and knowledge generation, and therefore do not produce significant waste streams. Data sharing and reuse among project partners further contribute to efficient resource use.
5. Prevention and reduction of air, water or soil pollution	Y	The project does not include activities that generate pollutants, hazardous waste, or emissions into air, water, or soil. Laboratory experiments were conducted under controlled conditions and in compliance with safety and environmental regulations. The proposed management strategies aim to reduce suspended sediment concentrations released downstream during flushing operations, thereby mitigating potential water quality deterioration.
6. Protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystem	Y	The project explicitly addresses ecological aspects by analysing the impacts of sediment management operations on river habitats. The modelling results support management solutions that reduce stress on aquatic ecosystems by favouring more frequent but less intense sediment flushing events, thus avoiding prolonged exposure to high sediment concentrations.

2.2. Consistency with the digital constraint

Max 500 characters

The activities carried out within the SMAHR project contribute to the digital transition through the extensive use of numerical modelling, digital data processing, and computational analysis. Hydrodynamic, sediment transport, and habitat models, as well as machine learning techniques, were applied to real case studies. Project expenses are directly linked to software tools, data management, modelling activities, and computational resources, ensuring full compliance with the digital objective and the digital constraint.

3. ECONOMICS RESULTS OF THE PROJECT

3.1. Project costs

Attach the final statement of costs incurred in connection with the project, indicating the type of cost incurred.

BUDGET			
	Final amount (€)	Initial assignment (€ - %)	Justification of the change in expenditure for the purposes of the project
Costs for specialist consultancy services	9503.31€	15000€ - 26%	The bathymetric sampling activities required lower expenses than initially budgeted. This was because the contract was awarded to the company offering the lowest price. In any case, the lower cost did not cause any issues for the continuation of the research activities.
Costs for materials, supplies and similar products	18236.01€	36500€ - 65%	Some purchases and rentals were not carried out because, during the course of the project, it was realized that they were not strictly necessary. Attempts were made to acquire other materials useful for the project, but it was not possible to fully spend the allocated budget. Additionally, some purchases could not be made because the PIV acquisition system stopped functioning, and its repair was neither feasible in time for project completion nor cost-effective due to very high maintenance costs.
Mission expenses	3847.23€	5000€ - 9%	Efforts were made to keep dissemination expenses as low as possible following the overall reduction of the project budget. Participation in the IAHR 2025 conference in Singapore was particularly costly due to the high registration fees, airfare, and accommodation expenses.
Total	31586.55€		

BUDGET			
	Final amount (€)	Initial assignment (€ - %)	Justification of the change in expenditure for the purposes of the project
RI -	16609.81€	29500€ - 52%	The costs allocated to RI are related to activities aimed at generating new scientific and technical knowledge and supporting the development of the numerical modelling framework of the project. In particular, bathymetric field activities were carried out to acquire geometric and morphological data required for the definition of the computational domain and for the calibration of the numerical models. Furthermore, the acquisition of advanced software tools and data storage systems enabled the processing, analysis and management of large datasets produced during the research activities. These activities are of a methodological and knowledge-driven nature and are not directly aimed at the construction or validation of final prototypes.
SS -	11129.51€	22000€ - 39%	The costs allocated to SS concern the implementation and operation of experimental setups derived from the knowledge generated during the RI phase. In particular, these costs include materials, components and modular structures required for the assembly of laboratory-scale experimental systems, as well as consumables and measurement equipment used during testing activities. Such expenses are necessary to perform controlled experimental tests and to support the experimental analysis of the developed solutions under representative conditions, without reaching the stage of full-scale implementation or commercial application.
Total	27739.32€		

4. SUMMARY OF TECHNICAL AND ECONOMIC CHANGES TO THE PROJECT (IF ANY)

Summarise the technical and financial changes that have been made to the project. Please note that, according to the call for proposals, changes must not substantially alter the objectives, results and impact of the initial project and must not lead to an increase in total expenditure. Please also specify whether the changes have an impact on the balance between the different types of expenditure.

During the course of the SMAHR project, some technical and financial adjustments were made without altering the overall objectives, expected results, or impact of the project.

Technical changes: Some planned purchases and rentals were not carried out because they were deemed unnecessary during project execution.

The PIV acquisition system became inoperative, and repair was neither feasible in time nor cost-effective, limiting some planned experimental activities.

Financial changes: Bathymetric survey costs were lower than budgeted due to a competitive tender. Savings from unneeded purchases and lower operational costs allowed the project to reallocate funds where possible without exceeding the total budget.

Efforts were made to minimize dissemination costs; for example, conference participation (IAHR 2025, Singapore) was particularly costly but accommodated within the overall budget.

Impact on expenditure balance: The adjustments slightly shifted the balance between categories (less on purchases and rentals, more on dissemination), but the total expenditure remained within the approved budget, and all key activities were successfully completed.

Overall, the changes improved cost efficiency and had no negative impact on the project's objectives, results, or expected impact.

5. IMAGES

Figure 1. Experimental velocity profile as found during the experiments conducted during the project.

Figure 2. Results of the simulation of a flood event on in hydropower reservoir. Example of how different management affects the sediment transport downstream the dam.

Figure 3. Preliminary results of effects of sediment flushing on the downstream habitat.

Figure 4. Preliminary results of Machine Learning approach to forecast the suspended sediment transport in catchment to calculate the incoming sediment in a reservoir.